

GIGONOMICS: DECODING THE MOTIVATIONS OF PAKISTANI GIG WORKERS IN THE DIGITAL MARKETPLACE

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Abstract

The current study was designed to focus on the factors that influence the individual to engage in gig work in the Pakistani digital marketplace. The present study attempts to address this gap and better explanation of gig work intentions through an extended social cognitive theory. To explore this phenomenon, data were collected through a structured questionnaire from Pakistani gig workers with a sample size of 315 participants. For data analysis, Amos and SPSS are used. The findings of this study revealed that extroversion and autonomy have a significant relationship with gig work intention, with the mediation of meaningful work, whereas need for achievement is treated as a moderator, strengthening the relationship and having a positive relationship with GWI. This study provides insight and guidance to the gig workers towards gig work intention by executing the different training programs and courses for gig workers. Furthermore, this study provides insight for future researchers to work with different moderators, such as different personality traits, and so on.

INTRODUCTION

With an increasing number of individuals working independently, outside of organizations, and in a style of work very unlike that expected by many organizational behavior theories, the way work is done has fundamentally altered in recent decades. To remain relevant, our research on individual work habits and the skills that support them must also change to reflect this brand-new labor market, the so-called "gig economy." (Ashford, Caza et al. 2018). It has been recorded by the Oxford Internet Institute (OII) that in 2017, Pakistan ranked 4th in the global digital gig marketplace, having almost 8% of the total freelance work. Pakistan is listed as the fourth fastest-growing market in the world for freelancers, generating \$500 million completely from the gig economy, positively influencing Pakistan's GDP. Due to temporary jobs, the labor market is having a dramatic change, which is mediated by online platforms, replacing standard employment. (Kässi and Lehdonvirta 2018). People are compelled to move towards the gig economy because of the increasing unemployment rate, so they are not able to find jobs that match their education and skills. (Dawson, Henley et al. 2009). As per the English dictionary, a gig worker is someone who is not a set employer. Gig work employment allows self-employed work. (ÇİĞDEM).

This study is to explore the key drivers that motivate an individual towards gig working in the gig economy. Local gig work and distant gig work are the two primary types of employment that make up the gig economy. Local gig work involves activities that are exchanged via online marketplaces but need the worker's actual presence at the job site. These positions might involve a variety of tasks and work. On the other side, remote gig work involves short-term agreements between employers and freelancers, made possible through online marketplaces like Upwork,

Amazon, Fiverr, and Freelancer.com. In this instance, since the task is being done remotely, the employee's personal presence is not required. (Wood, Graham et al. 2019). Students and individuals are motivated towards gig work as it provides them with opportunities to stretch their legs and apply their skills to something new, and some have the point of view that they can bear their own needs, and they can apply their skills on these platforms to earn bread and butter. (Massey and Elmore 2018).

On the other hand, some worker-centered factors motivate people, workers, and students to pursue gig work due to the variety of options. They get a chance to measure their interest in the service they are going to provide. These factors influence their behavior towards gig work, and due to satisfaction and alignment in interest and work, this trend is increasing. Here, the important point to understand is the factors of job quality, influencing individuals' responses to gig work, and recognizing how worker-centric factors motivate workers (Dunn 2020). In the context of Pakistan, it is unclear which factors influence the gig workers towards Gig work intention. This research is fivefold and will try to attain the stated objective. This study's first objective is to explore the effect of autonomy on gig work intention. However, this study will try to explore the extroversion effect on gig work intention. Research on the factors influencing gig working intention is hardly conducted in the context of Pakistan, and still, many questions are unanswered. As a further step, the study will help to explore the mediation role of meaningful work between extroversion and gig work intention. Moreover, the study will try to provide insight regarding the moderating effect of need for achievement on autonomy and gig work intention. Lastly, this study will also explore the moderating

effect on the relationship between meaningful work and gig work intention.

To address these issues, Anderson (2008) Work carried out an empirical investigation concentrating on the information gathering methods of managers. It suggests that variations in an individual personality attribute known as "need for cognition" might reflect the differences in how motivated people are to perceive and utilize the potential information benefits inherent in their social networks. The findings endorse that network features do, in fact, influence the advantages of information, but that these impacts are stronger for managers who are strongly driven to take advantage of these benefits. These results not only support the tenets of social capital theory but also highlight the important part that personality plays in improving social network analysis. So, social Cognitive theory is used to support the hypothetical framework because this theory emphasizes the reciprocal connection between a person's personal circumstances, environmental influences, and behavior, which is essential for understanding the factors influencing the intention to engage in gig work. (Bandura 1991). This theory contends that individuals' perceptions of their own skills (self-efficacy), their observations of others (vicarious learning), and their assessments of the results of their activities (outcome expectancies) all have a substantial impact on how they behave and make decisions. (Bandura 1999).

So basically, this study will provide an understanding of the complex interactions between personal characteristics like extroversion and the need for achievement, as well as environmental aspects like autonomy and meaningful work, and how these influences affect the intention to engage in gig work in the particular setting of Pakistan. This theoretical framework will contribute to the proposed field

of research by giving a thorough understanding of the factors and processes underlying one's intention to engage in gig work, as well as by shedding light on the potential mediation role of meaningful work and the moderating effect of need for achievement in the Pakistani economy.

Theoretical Background and Literature Review

Extraversion and Gig work intention

Recent research has unveiled a fresh perspective on the interplay between individuals' personality traits and their roles. This emerging understanding sheds light on how individual behavior patterns influence their networks. Researchers in this field have grappled with the task of pinpointing the fundamental personality traits that are linked to individuals occupying brokerage positions, such as whether it pertains to extraversion, a sense of power, or an entirely different personality trait altogether. (Landis 2016). The influence of personality traits, such as extraversion, on job-related behaviors and preferences, including the desire to engage in gig work. Extraversion is characterized by outgoing, vibrant, conversational behavior has been investigated. (Thompson 2008). Although extraverts may have an edge in team-based work, it is still unknown exactly what that advantage may be, how extraverts can achieve such an advantage, and under what circumstances. This is contrary to academic and practitioner literature, which have both made this claim. (Cullen-Lester, Leroy et al. 2016). According to research, extraversion may impact people's inclination for gig work. Individuals with high extraversion, for example, may be more motivated to seek out gig employment owing to the flexibility, liberty, and social contacts it provides. They may find gig work enticing as it allows them to interact with a diverse range of individuals and participate in multiple projects. Extraverted individuals

communicate more actively, such as by sending signals or making close eye contact. Recent research has examined this link in a digital world in a hedonic setting, such as Facebook profile pages. (Krämer and Winter 2008) And found that the aforementioned rationale holds for a digital environment as well. Furthermore, the study of Yang, Chen et al. (2023) Found that extraversion improves the link between career identity and career networking activities, and also takes into consideration personality factors. Moreover, gig workers were inclined towards the on-demand organizations.

Based on the recommended literature, we hypothesized:

H1: Individuals with higher levels of extraversion are more likely to have a stronger intention to engage in gig work.

Autonomy and Gig Work Intention

There is relatively limited research on gig workers, although data show that some people prefer the flexibility and independence of gig work. (Chen, Rossi et al. 2019). Meanwhile, a continuously increasing number of studies suggest that several groups involved in non-traditional work would prefer permanent employment to their present positions. Particularly, Boeri, Giupponi et al. (2018) study demonstrates that gig workers' actual behavior towards gig working is that they would like to work more hours. Whereas actual behavior can be indicated through the intentions of the single person (Ajzen 1991). So, through this, it can be understood which factors motivated students towards gig work. When compared to corporate occupations, gig work offers a great deal more control and freedom. Since they are self-employed, gig workers may organize their work to fit their own schedules and pick jobs that best suit their skill sets. Gig workers are autonomous, powerful, and independent. They disregard traditional

clothing codes, job schedules, and organizational hierarchy. They can control themselves and drive themselves (Nawaz, Zhang et al. 2019). Another study focused on how gig workers focus on the flexibility in schedule and work to accomplish their work (Hackston).

Talking about autonomy, it refers to the degree of independence in decision-making and tasks. (Sahoo, Behera et al. 2010)The intrinsic motivational factor of autonomy is crucial for improving knowledge sharing within an organization. (Foss, Minbaeva et al. 2009). Therefore, Gig work intention was depending on the flexibility and autonomy in work. Gig workers were having greater control over their working hours, choosing the projects which have to be pursued and taking the projects that offered having variety of roles. (Abubakar and Shneikat 2017, Seemiller and Grace 2017). Whereas it was founded by Jarrahi, Newlands et al. (2021) That variety of platforms of gig work was providing outreach to the global world. However, great challenges were also introduced with these platforms, such as a lack of control and a new form of precarity through the management system. These were the main constraints towards the autonomy that gig work intended and meaningful work, especially when there were rules such as account suspension, work assessment, and client control. In Gig work intention and autonomy there was the requirement of flexibility. Autonomy paradox has been discussed by the Mazmanian, Orlikowski et al. (2013)It's a platform in which workers have flexibility and autonomy, while simultaneously subjecting themselves to controlling information asymmetries and surveillance policies. The study suggested that if there was a high level of autonomy in Gig work intention, there were more chances of success for an individual in gig work. To support the conceptual

framework, this study gets support from social cognitive theory because this theory states that human motivation and action are extensively regulated by human forethoughts, with a line of crucial factors that influence human behavior. Under this concept of social cognitive theory, the literature is consistent with the concept of Bandura (1999). Based on the literature, we hypothesized that:

H2: The higher the level of autonomy perceived by an individual in gig work, the greater their intention to engage in gig work.

Meaningful work and Gig work intention

Although the gig economy is spreading all over the world, meaningful work varies from individual to individual. There is a huge discussion on this point about whether gig workers find meaningful work on the platform as compared to alternative options or not. To address this, there was a need to define the perception of the meaning of the work. (Nemkova, Demirel et al. 2019). Participants talked about actively redefining their perceptions of the types or nature of the tasks or relationships involved in their jobs, as well as reshaping their jobs to see them as a meaningful whole that positively impacts others, rather than a collection of discrete tasks, in the cognitive domain. (Berg, Wrzesniewski et al. 2010). Gig workers are giving their work more meaning as time goes on. (Goins 2015). Meaningful employment is seen as "a fundamental human necessity" in ethical literature. (Yeoman 2014). While Marxian political economy emphasizes the value of work as a means of realizing an individual's creative potential (Marx 1977).

In a holistic view, meaningful employment not only satisfies people's material (consumption) demands, but also gives them the flexibility and creativity. It is believed that employees who can find meaningful work by matching it

with their own interests, skills, values, and passions will also make a greater contribution to society through a deeper commitment to their jobs. Understanding meaningful work requires knowledge of both the work itself and the context in which it is performed. (Nemkova, Demirel et al. 2019).

Furthermore, the gig economy offers gig workers individuals having with disabilities new opportunities as well as difficulties in finding meaningful work. (Harpur and Blanck 2020). In gig work, several platforms, including crowdsourcing and others, have inspired researchers and practitioners, especially those in the human resources field, to look into ways to significantly raise gig workers' levels of job satisfaction through meaningful work while they work alone and primarily temporarily. (Connelly and Gallagher 2006). Even if these gig workers have a high level of autonomy and want to continue being self-initiated, HR professionals must consider the need to provide these gig workers a sense of purpose. It may also be seen as a factor in how meaningful gig workers feel their employment. (Mousa and Chaouali 2022). So, based on the above arguments, we hypothesized that:

H3: Meaningful work mediates the positive relationship between extroversion and gig work intention

Need for achievement and meaningful work.

The gig economy has grown dramatically in recent years, revolutionizing how people see employment and work. (Vallas and Schor 2020). Gig work has become a desirable choice for people looking for autonomous and alternative work arrangements as a result of the development of digital platforms and the rising need for flexibility. However, in order to fathom the motives and drives behind this changing gig work market, it is imperative for academics and practitioners to understand the elements that affect

people's desire to engage in gig employment. With an emphasis on the moderating impact of need for achievement, this literature review intends to analyze the important drivers and their interaction in determining people's intentions to engage in gig work. Through present studies, it has been revealed that the intricate connections between these variables offer a thorough knowledge of the thought processes and motivational forces that influence involvement with gig work.

In the relationship between meaningful work and intention to engage in the gig economy, the moderating effect of need for achievement, the results imply that people with a high demand for achievement have a greater positive association between their intention to perform odd jobs and what they consider to be meaningful work. The study emphasizes how crucial it is to take into account individual characteristics, such as a desire for achievement, when analyzing what drives people to participate in gig work. (Zaman and Qayyum 2020).

However, self-efficacy is used as a mediating variable to evaluate the moderating role of the demand for accomplishment in the link between meaningful work and gig work intention. In particular, when self-efficacy is high, the results show that people with a high demand for accomplishment feel a higher positive association between meaningful work and gig employment intention. The study emphasizes the interaction between the need for achievement with other variables in determining motivation for gig working. (Bogatyeva, Verkhovskaya et al. 2021). Furthermore, it has been investigated how the need for achievement moderates the association between entrepreneurial intent and meaningful work in the gig economy. The results show that people with a high demand for accomplishment exhibit a higher positive association

between their intention to pursue entrepreneurial endeavors within the gig economy and their perception of meaningful employment. This link is further strengthened by perceived market demand. The study emphasizes how important it is to include both personal and environmental factors when examining the intention to engage in the gig economy. (Lin, Au et al. 2020). The literature supports the hypothesis, so we stated that:

H4: Need for achievement moderates the relationship between meaningful work and Gig work intention

Need for Achievement and gig work intention.

Need for achievement has been considered an important personality trait that helps to determine individual behavior. (Tran and Von Korfflesch 2016). The regular behavior and performance have been studied on a suitable basis under a variety of domains. Although different studies have been done on gig work intention but still the results are still vague, and there is no systematic research on gig work intention and gig worker personality. But according to the literature, it is clear that gig workers do need achievement. (Patre 2022).

The need for achievement "seems to include expectations of achieving something better or quicker than anybody else or better than the person's previous accomplishments." The person is extremely hardworking and competitive, who has a desire to need for achievement (Hansemark 2003). According to the literature, it was very clear that the Gig work intention, gig workers had having high need for achievement, whereas financial rewards were considered as secondary achievement. (Williams and Curtis 2007). These people chose to work in the gig economy in order to be more independent and to learn and grow more quickly. Contrary to the majority, a small number actually mentioned the financial benefits of doing gigs as a crucial

consideration. These people discussed things like the tax benefits and the total pay increase. According to research, today's workers have more demanding jobs and are frequently required to put in longer hours than those who worked in earlier generations. (Bolino, Turnley et al. 2010). It has been determined that gig work intention and workers love expanding their knowledge and growing personally from the subject of development and learning. It can be viewed as a motivator in and of itself. However, it is also feasible to draw links to some underlying motivating elements, including a strong need for achievement, an internal center of control, and independence, as persons with a high need for achievement continually look for methods to improve themselves. (Karlsson and Wranne 2019). Whether one adopts the

viewpoint of Stephan, Hart et al. (2015) Or the perspective on underlying motivation, it is clear that development and learning are reasons for individuals to engage in the gig economy in the IT and business consulting sectors. Whereas giving gig workers a sense of autonomy for the regular tasks they perceive they are responsible for performing and the freedom to change their job duties, responsibilities, and schedules implies both an implicit appreciation of their abilities and a respect for their membership in the crowdsourcing platform they have chosen. They mostly interpret this as a feeling of meaningfulness and caring. (Mousa and Chaouali 2022). H5: Need for achievement moderates the relationship between autonomy and gig work intention

Hypothesized Framework

Methodology

The research employed a quantitative research design to investigate the factors influencing gig work intention. The study approach made it possible to analyze numerical data to find patterns, trends, and connections between variables, giving significant insights. A cross-sectional survey approach was used to gather data from a diverse sample of participants.

The target population for this study consists of individuals who are engaged in gig work or expressed an interest in gig work. Participants are selected using a convenience sample strategy from a variety of online gig work forums and internet platforms. The sample size is 315 participants. Data from the participants is gathered using a standardized questionnaire. The questionnaire has several parts, including ones for demographic data, Need for Achievement, Autonomy, Gig work intention, and Meaningful work. Participants' response was scored on five-point Likert scales that range from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

An online survey platform is used to gather the data, guaranteeing the privacy and anonymity of respondents. Email messages, social media posts, and online forums for gig employment all contained the survey link. To increase the response rate, participants got clear instructions and information about the study's goals. Furthermore, the individuals' demographic features are also examined using descriptive statistics. Inferential statistical methods like correlation analysis and regression analysis are used to analyze the connections between the variables with the help of SPSS and Amos software. Thus, the study made it possible to determine important determinants of the desire to engage in gig work as well as the kind, strength, and direction of the associations.

Measures

Extroversion

To measure the extroversion, a scale was adapted based on 9 items. (John and Srivastava 1999). Some are following: "I see myself as someone talkative", "I see myself as Someone Who Is reserved", "I see myself as Someone full of energy", and

"I have friends with whom I can share my joys and sorrows"

Need for Achievement

Need for achievement has been assessed by 6 items (Frs and Knox 1972) Which are opted for. Some Items are: "I know exactly what I want out of life", "In general, I try to make every minute count", and "Every day, try to accomplish something new."

Autonomy

The autonomy construct has been adapted from (Ahuja, Chudoba et al. 2007). Some items are: "In the team, I decide how to do my own work",

"I have a lot of freedom to decide how I perform assigned tasks," and "I set my own schedule for completing assigned tasks."

Gig work intention

The gig work intention construct has been adapted from the study of (Liñán and Chen 2009). Some of the Items are: "I am prepared to do anything to be a gig worker", "I am determined to start a gig career in the future" and "I strongly believe that I will start a gig career someday."

Meaningful work

The meaningful work construct has been adapted from (Spreitzer 1995, May, Gilson et al. 2004). The construct items are 6 in number. Some are following: “The work that

I do is important to me”, “The work I do is meaningful to me”, and “The work I do on this job is worthwhile”

Results

Table 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model	CMIN	DF	CFI	TLI	IFI	RMSEA
Five Factor Model	641.987	383	.941	.933	.941	.046

Confirmatory factor analysis is used to validate the five latent variables in a measurement model. The model fitness is measured with the help of numerous fit indices, including chi-square, comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), incremental fit index (IFI), and root mean square of approximation (RMSEA). It has been defined by Hu and Bentler (1999), a good model fit is having a CFI, TLI, and IFI value closer to 0.95; however, as per Kline (2023) The threshold value of RMSEA for model fit is less than 0.05. Whereas the accepted value of Chi-square must be less than 3. Table 1 has all the values which are meeting the threshold requirement ($\chi^2 = 641.98$; $df = 383$; $CFI = 0.941$; $TLI = 0.933$; $IFI = 0.941$; and $RMSEA = 0.046$) and are within the acceptable range.

As a result, CFA findings supported the model's satisfactory discriminant validity, so it is evident that model fit is

achieved and that all pertinent scale items are significantly loaded on their respective latent components.

Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE):

According to the study of Fornell and Larcker (1981) Composite reliability and average variance extracted are computed to evaluate the convergent and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is demonstrated if the CR value is greater than 0.60, while the allowed value range for the AVE is greater than 0.50. According to Table 2 findings, all constructions' CR and AVE values fall within the acceptable range. It is then said that all constructs have established a sufficient level of convergent validity. Additionally, the square root of the AVE is calculated to assess the discriminant validity, which should be higher than the correlation across latent variables, and the findings of Table 2 support the existence of discriminant validity.

Table 2. Correlation among Latent variables, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

S. No	Variable	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted	1	2	3	4	5
1	Extroversion	0.93	0.543	(0.728)				
2	Need for Achievement	0.94	0.567	.384**	(0.774)			
3	Meaningful work	0.97	0.555	.389**	.669**	(0.921)		
4	Gig work intention	0.96	0.614	.324**	.390**	.458**	(0.880)	
5	Autonomy	0.94	0.539	.289**	.477**	.613**	.400**	(0.840)

N=315, square root of AVE (Average Variance Extracted) are presented in p. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Off-diagonal values are the squared correlation among latent variables.

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Descriptive Statistics:

Table 3 measures and displays descriptive statistics for significant demographic parameters along with independent, mediating, and dependent variables of the

current investigation. Descriptive statistics include mean (M), standard deviation (SD), Cronbach's alpha, and correlation.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics, Correlation, and Reliabilities

S. No	Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Gender	1.43	.497										
2	Qualification	2.86	.868	.227**									
3	Experience	2.48	1.039	-.130*	.170**								
4	Income	3.45	2.624	.061	-.032	-.132*							
5	Age	2.06	.729	.037	.266**	.035	-.092						
6	Extroversion	27.8684	3.9879	-.062	-.062	.018	-.043	-.164**	(0.89)				
7	Need for Achievement	19.6101	3.6899	-.057	.021	.132*	-.171**	-.163**	.384**	(0.82)			
8	Meaningful Work	21.5921	3.7274	.090	.029	.059	-.059	-.110	.063	.069**	(0.97)	.034	-.045
	Gig Work Intention	15.1105	3.4894	.063	.069**	(0.97)	.034	-.045	.005				

10	Autonomy	12.9952	3.4294	.016	.016	.143*	.143*	-.132*	.289**	.477**	.613**	.400**	(0.95)
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N 315 Reliabilities are presented in parenthesis.

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing has been done through the structural equation modeling technique. Under this study it was observed that Hypothesis 1 there is positive and significant effect of extroversion on GWI ($\beta = 0.1231, p < 0.000$). Furthermore, results depict that (Hypothesis 2) Autonomy has positive and significant effect on Gig work intension ($\beta = 0.7718, p < 0.05$). The total effect of relationship between extroversion, meaningful work with Gig work intension is significant ($\beta = 0.2525, p < 0.000$). The results suggest that there is positive and significant relationship between meaningful work and GWI ($\beta = 0.3268, p < 0.000$). So far, the mediation is concerned, under hypothesis 3 with mediation analysis, it has been depicted that meaningful work is partially mediating the relationship between extraversion and the total effect which observed is ($\beta = 0.1295, p < 0.000$). In addition to it, same sign of LLCI and ULCI of indirect path supported the hypothesis with having same direction of LLCI and ULCI (0.0478, 0.1965). Both intervals are having same signs with no zero presence in them.

The moderation hypothesis states that need for achievement moderates the relationship between

meaningful work and gig work intension (hypothesis 4). According to this table 4 under moderating path the hypothesis is supported by the results wherein ($\beta = 0.1059, p < 0.05$) having same sign in LLCI and ULCI (-.0861, -.0463). The result shows that need for achievement is having significant effect on meaningful work and GWI. Specifically, we found that the relationship between extraversion and gig work intension is influenced by the degree of meaningful work and need for achievement. More specifically, those who are more extroverted, feel that their work is meaningful and have a strong need for achievement are more likely to intend towards in gig working.

Hypothesis 5 results suggests that there is significant positive effect on the interaction between autonomy, GWI moderated by individual need for achievement. Individuals with higher levels of autonomy, coupled with a strong need for achievement and perceiving their work as meaningful, are more likely to express a higher intention to engage in gig work.

Table 4. Path Analysis

Paths	β Coefficient
Extroversion → Gig Work Intention	0.1231***
Extroversion → Meaningful Work	0.3638***
Meaningful Work → Gig Work Intention	0.3268***
Extroversion → Meaningful Work → Gig Work Intention (Total Effect)	0.2525***
Autonomy → Gig Work Intention	0.7718**

Mediation Effect			
Indirect Paths	β Coefficient	LLCI	ULCI
Extroversion → Meaningful Work → Gig Work Intention	0.1295***	0.0478	0.1965

Moderating Effect			
Moderating Paths	β Coefficient	LLCI	ULCI
Extroversion → Meaningful Work * Need for Achievement → Gig Work Intention	0.1059**	-.0861	-.0463
Autonomy * Need for Achievement → Gig Work Intention	0.7524***	-.0309	-.0080

N = 315; bootstrap sample size = 5000; CI, confidence interval; UL, upper limit; LL, lower limit; ****p*<.000.

Figure 1: Interaction Graph of autonomy and need for achievement on GWI

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Under this analysis, the interaction graph (Figure 1) shows the moderation relationship between variables. As per this figure, the findings show that the need for achievement strengthens the relationship between autonomy and gig work intention. When there is low autonomy in gig work intention, there is low need for achievement, whereas when the level of autonomy is high, there is high need for achievement in individuals in gig work intention.

Whereas, as per Figure 2, if there is a high need for achievement, then the individual will be inclined towards

GWII; this means the moderator will strengthen the relationship between meaningful work and GWI. In contrast, if there were a low need for achievement, then the relationship would weaken between the MW and GWI.

Figure 2: Interaction Graph of meaningful work and need for achievement on GWI

Discussion

Despite a general discussion among researchers, the empirical evidence has shown various impacts on the work intention of gig workers. To build a better understanding of the gig work intention of gig workers, not only is the need for achievement a moderating role tested for some of the observed variation in effects, but also incorporates the hypothetical framework to make better understanding that how extroversion and autonomy play an important role with the help of mediation of meaningful work in the gig work intension of an individual.

Our findings clearly support the assertion that those individuals (Gig workers) who have a higher level of

extroversion are more inclined towards gig work intention. These findings support the idea that if an individual has the trait of being extroverted, it will lead to a desire for output towards gig work intention. Furthermore, the results of our study support the idea that if an individual has autonomy in work, it will lead to a higher intention towards GWI. In addition, we found support for the mediation (meaningful work) relationship between extroversion and GWI. Interestingly, our results show that moderation is also supported as per our hypothesis. Moderation (need for achievement) is influencing the observed variables. For example, researchers suggest that gig work intention, including businesses and the government, asserts that it

gives employees more autonomy, making it possible for those who may not otherwise have access to the workforce, such as women and the elderly, to obtain employment. (Klein 2017) .

Our results of H1 are consistent with the literature that a higher level of extroversion is more likely to have the intention of gig working. The searches included network concepts like centrality, brokerage, weak ties, and similar words, as well as psychological terms, including the Big Five, personality, characteristics, individual differences, and self-monitoring (Landis 2016). However, the existing literature on it demonstrates that the Big Five personality traits significantly predict job satisfaction. (Zhai, Willis et al. 2013). Extroverted individuals are more likely to be actively involved in social connections and exhibit gregarious, chatty, and assertive traits. Because they engage in more social interactions with their coworkers, people who are extroverted express higher levels of job satisfaction. As a result, they are more satisfied with their position at work. (Wang, Jackson et al. 2012). Results support the hypothesis and suggest that extrovert individuals are more likely to work as gig workers, and they have higher GWI.

In the same way, H2 is also consistent with the literature results are as per the predicted hypotheses, individuals with higher autonomy are more engaged in GWI. In the gig economy, autonomy is playing a crucial role as per. Monteith and Giesbert (2017) A study, in which focus groups were used to investigate the quality of jobs among informal sector workers in Sri Lanka, Burkina Faso, and Uganda. The study suggests that, in high-income countries, workers greatly value the autonomy and control over working hours traits as they are linked with high-quality employment. Shapiro (2018) The Study focused on local gig workers' autonomy over decisions about working hours and

order acceptance and rejection barely amounts to "autonomy over minute decisions. So, the results of H1 and H2 are consistent with the literature, and it is not wrong to claim that extroversion and autonomy play an important role in gig work intention.

Bawuro, Shamsuddin et al. (2019) study findings show that meaningful work mediates the relationship, as intrinsic motivation has been significantly improved with the quality of meaningful work. The results indicate that intrinsic motivation is a crucial variable in predicting how employees perceive their meaningful work, which suggests higher need for achievement with motivation increases the demand and desire for meaningful work. Moreover, our finding also supports this hypothesis (H3) that meaningful work mediates the relationship between extroversion and GWI. Meaningful work, considered as a motivational tool, is still in its infancy since academics have not yet experimentally looked at how it affects teachers' creative conduct (Staw 1990). Research conducted in Romania discovered that having meaningful work enhances workers' creativity, performance, and passion (Amabile and Pratt 2016). The original gig workers (professional musicians) are frequently not appropriately rewarded or acknowledged for the time and effort they devote to their art. So, the study reveals the strategies used by them to make sense of this challenging situation. To make sure their expectations are in line with the realities of their work, some people accept the undervaluing of their effort and interpret their triumphs as serendipity. Additionally, in order to cope with the devaluation of their art, musicians find meaning in their work and construct an idealized reality of their work (Lefcoe and Connelly 2022).

In H4 and H5, the result of the moderating effect of need for achievement in the relationship between meaningful

work and GWI and autonomy and GWI are in the expected direction. In both cases, the observed relationship is significant, and the moderation is high. The results indicate that the need for achievement is important to consider, as it is strongly impacting the gig worker's intention towards gig working. The study of Boud and Feletti (1998) Shows the need for achievement as a moderator, the impact of job demands for learning on job-related learning, because there is a tendency to take greater control of one's own job-related learning when achievement needs rise. An outcome of this sense of ownership for one's career-related learning is a propensity to use problem-based and action learning techniques. High goal setting has been associated with a high need for achievement. (Bandura 1991). Under the lens of social cognitive theory, extroversion and autonomy are influencing the gig workers towards gig work intention due to the degree of freedom and extroverted behavior. Taken all together, these findings, these results are generalizable in the Pakistani context. Gig work intention is influenced by personality traits such as extraversion, autonomy, perception towards meaningful work, and need for achievement. This research is consistent with the social cognitive theory, as we believe a significant process of self-directedness that has a significant influence on human thinking, affect, motivation, and behavior is included in the social cognitive theory of self-regulation. In a similar vein, the results of the current study offer a thorough overview of previous research and show that Gig work intention has a significant impact on personality traits with respect to social cognitive theory.

Practical Implication

On the basis of the results of this study, it has been recommended that there is a need to create training

programs for gig workers that will help them to become more extroverted. This may include seminars on client interactions, networking, and effective communication. Organizations can support gig workers to flourish in their jobs and experience greater success by giving them the tools and information to capitalize on their extroverted talents. Additionally, giving gig workers autonomy and giving them the chance to own their work may feed their drive for success. Providing them flexibility to make choices, take on difficult tasks, and show their knowledge can encourage a higher sense of self-accomplishment and happiness.

Limitations and Future Research

As with all research, our study is not without limitations. This study must be evaluated in light of a number of limitations. Firstly, extroversion, autonomy, and need for achievement desire may not be equally helpful for all gig workers. Some gig workers need introvert qualities like independence, concentrated work, analytical thinking, or specialized knowledge. Therefore, before assuming that extroverted features and a high demand for accomplishment are generally advantageous, it is important to acknowledge the diversity of gig workers and consider the unique requirements of each employment. Lastly, not every person is highly extroverted or has a strong drive for success. People have a variety of personalities and motives; thus, how successful they are at gig work may be influenced by a number of distinct characteristics and aspects. In order to avoid generalizing or assumptions regarding the viability of particular attributes for gig job success, it is crucial to consider a variety of individual variances. For future research, the moderator can be other variables, such as personality traits.

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